

Integrating Recycled and Alternative Materials in 3D Concrete Printing for Sustainable Development

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Suggested Citation

Prodhan, M.A.R., Hassan, A., Akter, M.J., & Muhammad, A. (2024). Integrating Recycled and Alternative Materials in 3D Concrete Printing for Sustainable Development. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 439-450.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).38](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).38)

Abstract:

3DCP changes the face of construction. It also increases design flexibility, independence from labor, and environmental sustainability. This paper presents research based on some 3DPCs replacing conventional materials with green concrete materials, including aggregates from waste, plastic and rubber materials, recycled glass, geopolymers, and supplementary cementitious materials. These materials reduce carbon emissions and resource depletion, with properties such as tensile strength and durability similar to or better than those of ordinary concrete. Several barriers still need to be overcome, such as material variability, while

mechanical anisotropy, scalability constraints, and high equipment costs are other significant factors. For 3DPC to play its full role in achieving the goals of sustainable construction, these barriers should be reduced to a minimum by mixing design optimization, standardization processes, and innovative production techniques.

Keywords: 3D concrete printing (3DCP), sustainable construction, recycled aggregates, geopolymer binders, eco-friendly materials.

Introduction

In recent years, the rapid growth of 3D concrete printing (3DCP) technology has brought about significant changes in the construction industry. Unlike traditional casting techniques, 3DCP enables concrete to be deposited layer by layer through extrusion. This method offers greater design flexibility, reduces reliance on labor, and enhances resource efficiency. Additionally, this

cutting-edge approach aligns seamlessly with global efforts to achieve sustainable development by tackling environmental and economic challenges in construction (Alami et al., 2023).

One of the most appealing aspects of 3DCP is its ability to incorporate alternative and sustainable materials, such as recycled aggregates, geopolymers, and bio-based fibers.

This reduces dependence on conventional resources like Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) and river sand. Research has shown that sustainable binders and recycled materials can lower carbon emissions while addressing critical issues such as resource scarcity and construction waste management (Kaszyńska et al., 2020).

As the most widely used construction material globally, concrete has a major environmental impact due to its significant carbon footprint. Even minor adjustments in its composition can make a notable difference in sustainability. For instance, alkali-activated materials and geopolymers have been found to enhance both environmental performance and mechanical properties, making them ideal for 3DCP applications (Bhattacharjee et al., 2021). These advancements pave the way for developing high-

performance, eco-friendly, and cost-efficient building materials.

Beyond material innovation, 3DCP provides substantial environmental and economic advantages. Research indicates that this technology can significantly reduce material wastage and operational costs while consuming less energy than traditional construction methods (Adaloudis & Bonnín Roca, 2021). Such benefits are crucial in meeting the global need for affordable and sustainable housing and infrastructure. As shown in Figure 1, 3DCP can achieve remarkable reductions in construction costs, water usage, and energy consumption, further highlighting its contribution to sustainable development goals (Alami et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Cost, Water, And Energy Reductions With 3DCP

Despite its promising potential, 3DCP faces challenges in material design, scalability, and regulatory acceptance. Such limitations and the need for mixed design optimization, which must balance sustainability with mechanical and rheological performance, drive the continued interest in research and innovation in this technology.

This paper investigates the incorporation of eco-friendly building materials into the 3DCP process. The study will emphasize the properties and challenges and discuss sustainability

opportunities regarding 3D-printed concrete. Based on state-of-the-art developments, this project advances further to develop the knowledge platform for advancing 3DCP applications toward practical uses for sustainable construction.

Application of Aggregates in 3D-Printed Environmentally Friendly Concrete

Due to the increasing demand for natural sand and gravel in recent years, these materials are gradually exhausted. Simultaneously, enormous quantities of construction waste, including concrete debris, are generated when removing old town buildings and municipal installations. Piling up and landfilling the given type of waste takes away land resources and seriously contaminates the urban environment. Therefore, it is urgent to find effective ways to

process construction waste and optimize its reuse. In-depth research into comprehensive utilization showed that replacing NA with RCA could be very important for the sustainable development of construction materials. Figure 2 below compares the GWP of various traditional materials with recycled rubber-based aggregates. The significant GWP reduction underlines the environmental benefit of material recycling in 3DCP (Sambucci et al., 2023).

Global Warming Potential (GWP) Comparison
(Source: Sambucci et al., 2023)

Figure 2. Global Warming Potential (GWP) Comparison

Plastic and Rubber Waste

Construction is a sector where great opportunities have arisen for sustainable development using discarded urban solid waste, mainly plastics and rubber. Effective utilization will save valuable raw resources and mitigate world environmental problems such as landfill overcapacity and plastic pollution. Concrete applications have evidenced that waste from plastics and rubber can partially replace natural aggregates to improve material properties and sustainability.

Butkutė et al. investigated the possibility of using secondary materials like waste plastic particles and waste foam rubber particles in concrete production. Tests performed by these authors revealed that waste foam rubber increased fresh mortar air voids and enhanced freeze-thaw

resistance. In this respect, such mixtures are particularly suitable for regions with cold climatic conditions where freeze-thaw resistance becomes an important factor in durability (Butkutė & Vaitkevičius, 2023).

Khatib et al. studied the structural behavior of concrete beams containing PW made from plastic bottle caps. Their test results showed that coarse aggregate replacement by PW at 10%, 15%, and 20% yielded an improved crack resistance. The initial cracking loads increased from 56 kN for conventional beams to 66 kN for concrete beams with 20% replacement through PW, showing strong bearing capacity and delaying the appearance of cracks (Khatib et al., 2020).

Korkut et al. similarly tested the behavior of PW as an acceptable aggregate replacement at

various levels: 0%, 5%, 15%, 30%, and 45%. Utilizing 3D finite element analysis, their findings showed that at early ages, some PW particles acted to enhance concrete strength. However, in more significant fractions, compacted PW results in a very slight loss of compressive strength due to greater porosity in the material.

Ground foam rubber, primarily sourced from recycled tires, has a few advantages from its light and flexible properties. It increases tensile splitting strength and freeze resistance due to increased ductility and higher energy-absorbing capacity. According to Sambucci et al., rubberized aggregates exhibit enhanced acoustic insulation and impact resistance, making them suitable for specialized soundproofing or vibration-dampening concrete applications.

Beyond the mechanical properties, both PW and FR aggregates contribute to the environmental arena by reducing industrial waste and increasing the sustainability of mixtures of 3D-printed concrete. These advances help apply the principles of the circular economy, where value is created from materials that would otherwise contribute to environmental degradation.

Recycled Sand

Recycled sand (RS) is mainly derived from construction and demolition waste and has lately appeared as an environmentally friendly alternative to natural sands for 3D-printed concrete. RS generally constitutes 25–40% of C&D waste and resolves some critical environmental problems involving excessive landfill use and depletion of natural aggregates. Some studies show that RS may improve buildability and green strength in 3D-printed structures by attaching highly hydrated cement paste to the recycled particles. Indeed, this paste will perform as an internal curing agent, enhancing early-stage performance during printing.

Mechanical properties of 3D-printed concrete with RS have been reported to be quite anisotropic due to the layer-by-layer construction technique. Accordingly, it is generally observed that optimum results are obtained at a 50% RS replacement ratio as both

compressive and tensile splitting strengths are favorably balanced in that proportion of RS. However, plastic shrinkage may increase at high replacement ratios, and workability can be adversely affected, raising challenges to practical applications. In overcoming these, admixtures of chemicals like sodium gluconate were engaged to prolong open times with improved adhesion between layers without sacrificing printability.

Although these few challenges are present, RS has significant environmental and mechanical benefits when applied in 3DPC. Introducing RS into the printing mixture reduces over-reliance on natural sand and adds weight to sustainable construction practices without seriously compromising the structural integrity of the printed elements. Further research into optimized mix designs and long-term durability continues to advance RS applications in sustainable construction (Zhang & Xiao, 2021).

Recycled Coarse Aggregates (RCA)

Recycled coarse aggregates (RCA) are essential for sustainable 3D-printed concrete. RCAs are sourced from construction and demolition (C&D) waste, reducing reliance on natural aggregates while addressing critical environmental concerns such as overuse of landfills and resource depletion. This innovative material aligns with the circular economy concept, ensuring ecological and economic benefits without compromising structural performance.

Including RCA in 3D-printed concrete significantly influences its mechanical and rheological properties. Research by Wu et al. highlights that RCA-based concrete exhibits exponential development of yield stress with resting time, positively impacting buildability, particularly during the early critical stages of printing. The shear modulus also increases linearly, ensuring the stability of the material under its weight and subsequent layers (Wu et al., 2021). These properties make RCA concrete well-suited to the demands of extrusion-based 3D printing.

Regarding mechanical performance, RCA has demonstrated satisfactory compressive strength and low shrinkage properties comparable to

conventional concrete. Lotfi et al. found that compressive strengths similar to natural aggregate concrete can be achieved with RCA replacement levels up to 100%, provided proper mix designs are implemented. RCA's water absorption also allows for internal curing, reducing shrinkage-induced cracking and improving long-term durability (Lotfi et al., 2015).

Economically, using RCA has significantly reduced concrete production costs by decreasing reliance on natural aggregates and reducing cement demand. Its incorporation into 3D-printed structures has also been shown to lower the carbon footprint, supporting greener construction practices (Han et al., 2021). While challenges such as variability in aggregate properties and impacts on flowability remain, advancements in mix design optimization continue to address these issues effectively.

Ultimately, RCA is a prime example of how waste materials can be creatively repurposed to support sustainability in construction, particularly in 3D printing applications. It has emerged as a valuable material for the future, balancing environmental benefits with performance requirements in sustainable construction.

Recycled Glass

Recycled glass increasingly finds its place in 3D-printed concrete as a valid, sustainable alternative to natural aggregates, with environmental and mechanical advantages. Recycled glass aggregates derived from post-consumer waste alleviate the depletion of natural resources and address the problems of non-biodegradable glass disposal. Using recycled glass effectively in 3DCP requires appropriate particle size and gradation to balance rheological, mechanical, and durability properties.

Research has proven that recycled glass aggregates improve concrete printability by enhancing flowability and buildability. Ting et al. found that incorporating fine glass aggregates reduces static yield stress, enhancing permeability and extrusion in printing. However, higher dosages of recycled glass led to increased plastic viscosity and reduced interlayer bonding, emphasizing the need for mix design optimization (Ting et al., 2019).

Considerable research has also focused on the mechanical performance of concrete made with recycled glass. Replacing 50% of natural sand with glass aggregates has improved flexural and compressive strengths, particularly when the glass particles are finely ground to reduce alkali-silica reactivity (ASR). This reduction in expansion and cracking helps maintain structural integrity over time (Cuevas et al., 2021). Additionally, the angular shape of glass particles enhances bonding between the aggregate and cement paste, boosting tensile strength, freeze-thaw resistance, and suitability for use in cold climates (Mansour et al., 2023).

However, challenges such as increased porosity and reduced compressive strength arise at higher replacement ratios. Future research should explore hybrid aggregate systems that combine recycled glass with natural or artificial aggregates to address these issues. Tailored mix designs, incorporating chemical additives like sodium gluconate, can extend printability windows and improve layer bonding (Annapareddy et al., 2018).

In conclusion, recycled glass aggregates offer a promising pathway toward sustainable construction with 3DCP. By optimizing mix designs and overcoming existing challenges, recycled glass can successfully deliver both environmental and structural benefits for modern construction.

Table 1. Sustainable Materials and Their Benefits for 3D Concrete Printing

Material	Benefits	Challenges	References
Recycled Aggregates	Reduces landfill waste, decreases cost, and lowers carbon footprint.	Inconsistent quality and reduced mechanical properties.	(Han et al., 2021)

Geopolymer Binders	Reduces CO2 emissions, enhances durability, and achieves higher compressive strength.	Material variability and difficulty in activator control.	(Bhattacharjee et al., 2021)
Plastic and Rubber Waste	Addresses pollution and improves durability and freeze-thaw resistance.	Reduces compressive strength when used in higher proportions.	(Butkutė & Vaitkevičius, 2023)
Recycled Glass	It improves flowability, enhances mechanical properties, and reduces natural aggregate use.	Increases plastic shrinkage and porosity at higher replacement levels.	(Bai et al., 2021)
Supplementary Cementitious Materials (SCMs)	It decreases reliance on Ordinary Portland Cement and improves rheology, durability, and environmental performance.	SCM availability is becoming limited, with inconsistent performance in some regions.	(Fonseca & Matos, 2023)

Table 1 illustrates how different sustainable materials contribute to 3DCP applications. Each material offers distinct advantages, such as reducing carbon emissions or enhancing mechanical properties, while presenting unique challenges like variability in quality or reduced performance under certain conditions. These factors highlight the importance of ongoing research and innovation to overcome limitations and maximize the potential of 3DCP in sustainable construction.

Application of Cementitious Materials in 3D-Printed Environmentally Friendly Concrete

Supplementary Cementitious Materials (SCMs)

SCMs are crucial in making 3D-printed concrete (3DPC) more sustainable. These materials, such as fly ash, silica fume, and ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBFS), serve as substitutes or supplements to Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), significantly reducing OPC usage while enhancing concrete properties like durability, workability, and long-term strength. By incorporating industrial by-products, SCMs promote sustainable construction practices and contribute to lower carbon emissions.

Research highlights that binary and ternary blends of SCMs optimize the rheological behavior of concrete by improving parameters such as yield stress, plastic viscosity, and resistance to phase separation. For instance, with its ultra-fine particle size, silica fume enhances the shape stability of freshly printed layers and

reduces bleeding. Fly ash increases workability and minimizes early-age shrinkage due to its pozzolanic properties, which help densify the concrete's microstructure (Butkutė et al., 2023). Additionally, combining GGBFS with silica fume has enhanced compressive strength and resistance to chloride ion penetration, both critical for durable 3D-printed structures (Panda et al., 2019).

Figure 3 illustrates the compressive strength achieved with various sustainable cementitious mixes optimized for 3D concrete printing. Fly ash-based mixes stand out, showcasing excellent performance and reinforcing their potential as an environmentally friendly alternative (Wang et al., 2022).

SCMs also affect the extrudability and buildability of 3DPC. Calcined shale ash can be added to concrete mixes to shorten the setting time, thus enabling faster layer deposition without affecting the structural integrity of such concrete. On the other hand, ultra-fine fly ash reduces yield stress and viscosity, ensuring better flow during printing while maintaining the dimensional accuracy of the printed elements.

The challenges with SCMs involve consistency in material quality and industrial by-product variability. However, advances in mixed design methodologies and testing protocols continue to surmount these challenges, enabling their broader applications in 3DPC.

In conclusion, SCMs are one of the viable pathways to improve not only the environmental but also the mechanical performance of 3D-printed concrete. The incorporation of SCMs into 3DPC will contribute to the formation of

new environmentally friendly construction practices and the enhancement of the quality of durability in printed structures.

Figure 3. Compressive Strength of Optimized Mixes

Geopolymer Binders

Geopolymer binders currently have great potential to find applications in 3DPC owing to their possibility of providing a sustainable alternative to OPC. Geopolymers synthesized by alkali activation of source materials such as fly ash, slag, and metakaolin show significant improvements in mechanical and durability properties compared to OPC, associated with a drastic reduction in CO₂ emissions. The main features of geopolymers are their rapid setting time and excellent workability, which makes them suitable for layer-by-layer construction that characterizes 3D printing.

The high speed at which geopolymers are set eliminates using accelerators, improving their buildability in 3DPC applications. For example, Hájková et al. noted that an optimized geopolymer composite for 3D printing applications could attain a setting time of 50 minutes, yielding sufficient workability for extrusion and placement of layers. At room temperature, the material has attained compressive strengths of up to 70 MPa,

demonstrating its structural viability (Hájková et al., 2023).

The rheological properties of geopolymer binders are of prime importance to ensure printability and structural stability. Barve et al. identified the critical issue of reaching an optimal balance in yield stress and viscosity for maximum permeability and extrusion in a study. Based on their findings, geopolymers with lower viscosity enhance flowability, while adequate yield stress maintains shape retention during printing (Barve et al., 2023).

Geopolymers lessen the environmental impact on construction in terms of a decrease in the level of greenhouse gas emissions while influencing the improvement in structural properties of 3DPC. According to Meskhi et al., the denser aluminosilicates' microstructure, which takes place during polymerization, decreases shrinkage, porosity, and water absorption, hence increasing long-term durability. Their results showed that geopolymer concrete could decrease CO₂ emissions up to 80% compared to OPC, indicating the main

contribution of the geopolymer to sustainable construction (Meskhi et al., 2023).

Geopolymer printing faces challenges, including material variability and precise control of activator ratios. Recent developments have included using sodium and potassium hydroxides in combined form as activators, improving workability while maintaining consistency. Current research is furthering this effort on mix design optimization and hybrid binder systems to extend the geopolymers' applications into more geometrically complex structural designs (Al-Abdwais, 2023).

In conclusion, geopolymer binders represent a revolutionary approach to sustainable construction, combining environmental benefits with corresponding performances required for the most recent advanced 3D printing technologies. Further efforts will be devoted to overcoming the present challenges and exploiting their potential in eco-friendly construction.

Application of Fibers in 3D-Printed Environmentally Friendly Concrete

Fibers fortify 3D-printed green concrete to enhance weak points such as tensile strength, poor interlayer adhesion, and anisotropic cracking from successive layer printing processes. Adding fibers to printed concrete increases mechanical properties, ductility, and durability, making it ideal for various structural applications. Both synthetic and natural fibers strengthen the structural integrity of concrete and contribute to sustainability by reducing reliance on traditional reinforcement methods. For instance, steel fibers enhance printed elements' flexural and tensile strength while reducing shrinkage-induced cracking and thermal deformation, making them suitable for high-performance applications (Pham et al., 2023). Additionally, polypropylene fibers improve workability during printing and offer crack-bridging capabilities, ensuring better dimensional stability in printed structures (Ramezani et al., 2023).

Natural fibers, such as jute and hemp, have garnered interest due to their eco-friendly attributes. These fibers enhance thermal insulation, fire resistance, and impact toughness while lowering the carbon footprint of concrete. Research indicates that natural fiber-reinforced 3D-printed concrete surpasses synthetic fibers in sustainability metrics, making it an excellent choice for green construction projects (Salmabanu et al., 2023). Innovations in continuous fiber integration, such as flow-based pultrusion techniques, have enabled using long, aligned fibers like carbon and glass, further boosting the mechanical performance of 3D-printed concrete. These continuous fibers increase tensile strength and ductility, creating large-scale load-bearing components and bridging the gap between research and industrial applications (Caron et al., 2023).

Despite these advantages, incorporating fibers into 3D-printed concrete presents challenges, such as reduced workability at high fiber content and the need for precise dispersion to prevent clustering. Excessive fiber content can lead to blockages in printing equipment and uneven layer deposition. However, hybrid fiber systems, which combine synthetic and natural fibers, show promise in addressing these issues by balancing properties while maintaining printability and mechanical performance. Future research should focus on optimizing fiber-matrix interactions, improving interlayer bonding, and developing cost-effective fiber processing methods to promote wider adoption of green construction practices.

Challenges and Limitations of 3D-Printed Environmentally Friendly Concrete

Adopting 3D-printed environmentally friendly concrete (3DPCE) faces numerous challenges that span material properties, technology limitations, and practical constraints. Addressing these issues is essential for achieving its full potential in sustainable construction. As shown in Figure 4, 3DPCE demonstrates notable efficiency improvements, including significant contributions to material reduction, energy

savings, and recycling promotion. These metrics align with the principles of sustainable construction (Rudziewicz et al., 2023).

Figure 4. Efficiency Metrics With 3DCP

- Material Variability:** Using recycled aggregates and industrial by-products in 3DPC often results in variability, leading to inconsistencies in mechanical properties, rheology, and durability.
- Mix Optimization:** Achieving the right balance between extrudability, buildability, and strength demands exact mix designs and advanced testing protocols.
- Impact of Additives:** While high fiber content and other additives enhance mechanical properties, they often reduce flowability and can cause clogging in extrusion nozzles, which affects overall printability.
- Anisotropic Mechanical Properties:** The layer-by-layer printing process introduces directional strength variations, with interlayer bonding being weaker than within-layer strength.
- High Equipment Costs:** The expensive nature of advanced 3D printing equipment limits its feasibility for large-scale or budget-sensitive projects.
- Low Production Speeds:** Current 3D printing technologies are characterized by slow production rates, making them less practical for high-demand or large-scale construction.
- Standardization Gaps:** The absence of comprehensive standards for testing, material specifications, and quality control creates challenges for broader adoption in the construction industry.
- Environmental Trade-offs:** Although geopolymers and recycled materials significantly reduce carbon emissions, the processes of sourcing and processing these materials can sometimes offset the environmental benefits.
- Scalability Constraints:** The technology is mainly limited to small-scale or prefabricated elements due to the challenges associated with printing and transporting more significant components.

Conclusion

3D-printed environmentally friendly concrete represents using innovative materials and top printing technologies to create a more sustainable construction approach. This method focuses on reducing carbon footprints and optimizing resource utilization. Incorporating recycled aggregates, geopolymers, and fibers has demonstrated significant potential to enhance the mechanical performance, durability, and sustainability of 3DPC. However, key challenges such as material variability, anisotropic strength differences, high equipment costs, and scalability limitations remain significant obstacles to its broader application.

Addressing these challenges will require a hybrid approach that integrates material science advancements, cutting-edge printing technology, and standardized industry protocols. Innovations such as hybrid material systems, automated production methods, and collaborative efforts to establish universal standards and regulations will be essential to unlocking 3DPC's full potential. With continued research and development, 3DPC is poised to revolutionize construction practices, aligning them more closely with sustainability principles and environmental responsibility.

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